

Unintentional Information Blocking: A Longitudinal Analysis of Availability Failures in mHealth (2011-2025)

Timoteo Kelly

Institute for Data Science & Informatics
University of Missouri-Columbia
Missouri, USA
tkb5b@missouri.edu

John Robert Bautista

Sinclair School of Nursing and Institute for Data Science & Informatics
University of Missouri-Columbia
Missouri, USA
jbautista@missouri.edu

Abstract—The confidentiality, integrity and availability (CIA) triad of the HIPAA Security Rule serves as a model for the protection of Protected Health Information (PHI). Among its three pillars, health informatics research has traditionally placed less emphasis on availability - the principle wherein authorized users should always have reliable and timely access to systems. In this study, we focus on the availability component by examining health consumers’ reviews of mobile health (mHealth) applications that store and process PHI, such as patient portals and telehealth apps. Specifically, we performed a longitudinal analysis of 480,450 user reviews from the HARPT dataset to uncover availability trends. We restricted the data to 249,425 reviews classified with more than 90% confidence to ensure quality. Our results show an availability gap, with technical reliability complaints (login failures or crashes) rising sharply from 18% in 2017 to 38% in 2025. We also observe security friction (technical barriers impeding secure access but incentivizing non-secure workarounds) in which users report high trust in provider care (Competence, 4.65 stars) despite increasing reliability complaints (Reliability, ~50% 1-stars). Our results show that technical unreliability when accessing mHealth apps is a fundamental security failure involving PHI because this creates barriers to availability and can be interpreted as unintentional information blocking, which is a direct violation of the 21st Century Cures Act.

Index Terms—*Human-Centered Cybersecurity, mHealth, Availability, Security Friction, Patient Portals, Telehealth, Apps*

I. INTRODUCTION

The ubiquitous adoption of mobile health (mHealth) applications (apps) has drastically changed health systems by enhancing access and delivery of healthcare services. The Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability (CIA) triad is a fundamental model in information security that is expressed through the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Security Rule [9]. Although most mHealth apps are not HIPAA-certified or compliant, some mHealth apps that process Protected Health Information (PHI), such as patient portals and telehealth apps, must adhere to the CIA triad to protect users’ privacy. Thus, the CIA triad serves as a crucial guide for the mHealth ecosystem because even apps that do not handle PHI can follow it to ensure user trust.

Health informatics research has primarily focused on the two pillars of the triad: Confidentiality which is protecting data privacy, and Integrity which is ensuring data accuracy. A narrow focus on these first two pillars often overlooks the third: *Availability*, which dictates the timely and reliable access to and use of information by the user [18]. When accessing PHI, users should have the ability to access secure platforms without excessive friction. When access to these platforms fails due to technical failures, this is considered a functional security failure. Under the 21st Century Cures Act, *Information Blocking* is defined as any practice likely to interfere with, prevent, or materially discourage the access, exchange, or use of PHI [11]. While often discussed as a policy or interoperability issue, our research highlights a technical form of information blocking: where poor app performance and unreliable access act as structural barriers that deny users the access they are legally entitled to. Thus, in this study, we operationalize *Technical Reliability* as the functional proxy for Availability within the CIA triad.

This paper argues that mHealth apps that store and process PHI, such as patient portals (to access medical records) and telehealth (to set virtual appointments and receive health care) face a critical gap in Availability. By analyzing > 480,000 user reviews across patient portal and telehealth apps available on the Google Play Store, we investigate whether these mHealth apps meet the Availability requirement. Our research is guided by the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** Do mHealth apps that process PHI demonstrate technical maturity (stability) over time or reliability regression?
- **RQ2:** How do availability failures impact user reviews of mHealth apps that process PHI?
- **RQ3:** Is the frequency of availability failures different between patient portal and telehealth apps?

II. RELATED WORK

A. RQ1: The Maturity Hypothesis

First proposed by Nolan [1], Stage Hypothesis posits technical stability over time. Specifically, Nolan proposed that

TABLE I.
HARPT classes with descriptions and examples. We map Reliability from our framework to Availability.

Label	Description	Example
Data Control (Privacy Concerns)	Concerns about consent, third-party access, or control over personal data.	<i>"It's great the app lets me review and delete my medical records whenever I want."</i>
Data Quality (Privacy Concerns)	Issues with incorrect, outdated, or incomplete health data.	<i>"The app is showing someone else's health record!"</i>
Reliability (Availability) (Trust in Application)	App crashes, login failures, or inconsistent functionality.	<i>"I can't login! Every time I enter my username and password it just loads and loads."</i>
Support (Trust in Application)	User experience with help services or communication.	<i>"Customer support responded to my query within a few hours and helped me resolve my issue."</i>
Risk (Trust in Application)	Worries about security, breaches, or misuse of data.	<i>"I'm worried about how the app stores my personal health records."</i>
Competence (Trust in Provider)	Perceptions of provider professionalism and care quality.	<i>"I received tailored advice based on my health data and it helped me manage my condition better."</i>
Ethicality (Trust in Provider)	Judgments of provider fairness, transparency, or responsibility.	<i>"I love that the app asks for my consent before collecting my data."</i>

over time, IT systems will inevitably evolve from an initial chaotic state, known as Contagion, into its final state of stability, referred to as Maturity. This assumption of linear stabilization for IT systems has then been adopted by modern healthcare maturity models [2], [10]. In these established frameworks, system availability and reliable access are explicitly treated as foundational prerequisites for achieving higher-level technological maturity. Thus, prior literature establishes a direct relationship between healthcare system maturity and its availability stabilization.

This leads to RQ1, which investigates whether our selected mHealth apps still align with Nolan's maturity expectations. We test whether mHealth apps follow this linear progression or if the introduction of additional features and complexities has caused a regression.

B. RQ2: User Choice and "Switching"

Previous studies on continued use emphasize the agency of the user. In their study, Vaghefi and Tulu [3], proposed a framework where users with Low Assessment (dissatisfaction) would simply switch to a better alternative. This framework assumes there is an open competitive marketplace where users can vote with their adoption choice. However, this logic fails for patient portal and telehealth apps. A user cannot simply switch from their provider's official platform (e.g., a user cannot abandon *MyChart* if their hospital requires it to access medical records). When switching is not an option, the *High Persistence / Low Assessment* cohort identified by Vaghefi and Tulu [3] is forced to endure the friction rather than migrate.

Because these captive users cannot abandon the failing app, their primary recourse for expressing dissatisfaction is in the public app reviews. Consequently, RQ2 examines how this lack of agency impacts user reviews, positing that availability failures will disproportionately drive severe negative feedback as users penalize the structural barriers they are forced to use.

C. RQ3: Platforms and Privacy-Availability Tension

Previously the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) community has prioritized the Confidentiality pillar of the CIA triad. Recent studies use automated extraction to identify user concerns regarding data sharing and "privacy calculus" [8], [17]. However, the CIA triad defines Availability as an equal security requirement [9]. We believe that the current research focus is lopsided. While privacy protections have matured, system availability has degraded, potentially violating the spirit of Information Blocking regulations. This imbalance may not be the same across the entire mHealth ecosystem. For instance, telehealth apps' marketplace is more competitive, but patient portals are rigidly tied to specific providers. This leads to RQ3, which investigates whether the frequency of availability failures differs between patient portal and telehealth apps.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

We utilize HARPT (Health App Reviews for Privacy & Trust), a large scale, peer-reviewed dataset constructed to analyze privacy concerns and trust among patient portal and telehealth app users [12]. To clarify the scope of our analysis, the data for this study was processed in two distinct phases.

First, to build the foundational HARPT database, we used a Python pipeline to scrape reviews from the Google Play Store, targeting 67 mobile health apps (36 patient portals, 31 telehealth). This collection yielded 480,450 reviews that span from September 2011 to April 2025. This time frame captures the pre-pandemic baseline, the rapid COVID-19 expansion, and the post-pandemic stabilization phase. Second, for the specific analysis of availability failures in this study, we extracted a targeted subset of 249,425 reviews. This subset was specifically isolated because every review within it was classified by our pipeline with greater than 90% confidence.

By restricting our focus to this high-confidence subset, we can accurately evaluate how application maturity affects tech-

nical reliability without the noise of the broader foundational database.

This study did not require IRB approval as it constitutes non-human subject research. The complete dataset and our ground-truth model training data are publicly released on Harvard Dataverse [13].

B. Analysis Plan

To address our research questions, we analyzed the high-confidence dataset in several steps. For **RQ1**, we mapped the longitudinal trajectory of technical stability by calculating the annual proportion of *Availability* reviews. For **RQ2**, we cross-tabulated predicted semantic classes with user star ratings to quantify the severity of dissatisfaction (specifically 1-star reviews) driven by availability failures. For **RQ3**, we segmented the dataset by platform type (Patient Portals vs. Telehealth) and applied a Chi-square test of independence to compare the proportion of availability complaints between platforms.

C. Taxonomy & Theoretical Framework

To categorize the user reviews, we used a novel seven-class taxonomy derived by synthesizing constructs from previous foundational models (see Table I).

- **Trust in Application.** This construct is grounded in McKnight et al.’s work on trust in technology [6] and healthcare-specific trust models [14] [15] which emphasizes beliefs about a system’s reliability, helpfulness, and functionality. It also incorporates Gefen et al.’s integration of trust with technology acceptance [28], highlighting the influence of risk.
 - *Reliability*: In this study, we operationalize this class as *Technical Reliability* and is the functional proxy for Availability. Reliability captures user experiences of technical stability, such as app crashes, login failures, or inconsistent functionality.
 - *Support*: Reflects user experiences with help services, communication, or support materials.
 - *Risk*: Addresses worries regarding security, potential breaches, or the misuse of data.
- **Trust in Provider.** We distinguished trust in the healthcare provider from trust in the application by building on Mayer et al. [7], who identify ability, benevolence, and integrity as key antecedents of trust. We also drew on Hosmer [32], who emphasizes fairness and ethical responsibility.
 - *Competence*: This is mapped from Mayer’s *ability*. It represents perceptions of provider professionalism and care quality.
 - *Ethicality*: This is mapped from *integrity* and fairness. It captures judgments of provider transparency, responsibility, and consent.
- **Privacy Concerns.** Adapted from the Internet Users’ Information Privacy Concerns (IUIPC) [27], ubiquitous computing concerns [29], as well as general privacy [25] and healthcare-focused privacy research [23] [26], these theories motivate our focus on data governance:

- *Data Control*: Models user concerns regarding consent, third-party access, and control over personal data.
- *Data Quality*: Addresses issues related to incorrect, outdated, or incomplete health data.

D. Machine Learning Pipeline

Manual annotation of the entire 480,450 dataset was infeasible. We utilized a weak supervision strategy using the transformer-based model, XLNet [22].

- 1) **Ground Truth.** A subset of 4,000 reviews was manually annotated by a four-person team using a three-pass verification protocol, achieving a strong inter-rater reliability (Fleiss’ Kappa = 0.877).
- 2) **Data Augmentation.** To address class imbalance, we applied back-translation (English to French, German and Spanish to English) to generate synthetic minority samples, creating a balanced training set of 7,000 reviews.
- 3) **Model Training.** We fine-tuned an XLNet model on the balanced ground truth. The model achieved an overall F1-score of 0.867 and demonstrated high calibration accuracy (98.3%) in the highest confidence bin.

In the interest of reproducibility and further research, we publicly release both our full dataset and ground truth dataset for model training [12].

E. Confidence Filtering

To maintain the validity of our findings, we restricted our study to predictions with a model confidence score of > 0.9 . This filtering process retained 249,425 high-confidence reviews (51.9% of the total dataset), minimizing the noise inherent in weak supervision labeling. This ensures that our trend analysis reflects genuine user sentiment.

TABLE II.

Dataset Characteristics showing > 0.9 confidence subset.

Metric	Value	% Distribution
Total Reviews	249,425	100%
Star Rating Distribution		
5-Star (Positive)	150,154	60.2%
1-Star (Negative)	54,125	21.7%
Top Semantic Labels		
Competence	111,742	44.8%
Availability	78,569	31.5%
Data Control	30,430	12.2%

IV. RESULTS

A. Dataset Characteristics

The high confidence dataset is heavily skewed toward positive sentiment (60.2% 5-star ratings), see Table II. This mirrors the skew of the full dataset. The negative sentiment is particularly significant. Competence remains the most frequent category (44.8%), followed closely by Availability (31.5%).

B. The Availability Gap (RQ1)

Our analysis reveals a concerning *U-shaped* regression in technical reliability (Fig. 1).

- **The Maturity Phase (2011–2017).** Availability complaints steadily declined to a historic low of $\sim 18\%$ in 2017, suggesting a period of platform stabilization.
- **The Regression Phase (2018–2025).** This trend reversed sharply. Beginning in 2018 and accelerating through the pandemic, availability complaints surged, climbing to **38%** of all reviews by 2025.

Fig. 1. Availability complaints was 18% in 2017 and surged to **38%** in 2025, indicating a regression in system stability.

C. Security Friction (RQ2)

Fig. 2 isolates the intensity of user dissatisfaction. While *Competence* reviews have a negligible 1-star rate ($< 5\%$), *Availability* reviews exhibit a $\sim 50\%$ 1-star rate. Furthermore, *Ethicality* violations, though rare, are punished most severely ($> 80\%$ 1-star).

Additionally, although *Ethicality* has a high rate of negative sentiment, Fig. 2 reveals the true scale of the problem. *Availability* issues generated 39,223 negative reviews, dwarfing all other categories combined. This reveals that users are $7.4x$ more likely to encounter technical availability failure rather than failure of provider care.

D. The Portal Problem (RQ3)

Fig. 3 shows differences in the proportion of issues between patient portals and telehealth apps. Our results show that patient portals (37%) have a significantly higher ($\chi^2(1) = 6,429.48, p < 0.001$) proportion of availability failures than telehealth apps (22%).

V. DISCUSSION

Our analysis of the 249,425 high-confidence reviews reveals a systemic availability regression for patient portal and telehealth apps. Overall, the industry has made strides in Confidentiality and Integrity, but our results indicate that Availability is failing.

Fig. 2. Availability issues generate $7.4x$ more negative reviews than Competence issues.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the classes per platform. Availability is more frequently discussed among users using patient portals versus discussions of provider care for telehealth.

A. The Regression of Availability

Our findings do not support Nolan’s “Stage Hypothesis” [1] for the mHealth ecosystem. The hypothesis predicts a linear trajectory from Contagion (chaos) to Maturity (stability). However, contrary to this, our data (RQ1) shows a U-shaped line where the ecosystem achieved stability in 2017 (only 18% of complaints were related to Availability) but has since regressed into a second phase of instability (38% in 2025). While more granular research through topic modeling may

reveal latent sub-themes that help us understand the specifics of the negative Availability reviews, the data could suggest a rapid integration of more complex features (such as real-time scheduling, multi-factor authentication, etc), has outpaced the stability of the underlying infrastructure.

B. Availability Issues as Information Blocking

The surge in Availability complaints for users shows that this friction constitutes a functional security failure. Information Blocking is the practice that prevent the exchange, access or use of PHI. Recent studies by Everson and Healy [31] discuss the fact that technical barriers remain a primary source of information blocking.

Our results validate this on a large scale, when issues with patient portals crashes during login, the provider is unintentionally blocking access to PHI. By failing to maintain Availability, providers are effectively violating the federal interoperability mandates and the 21st Century Cures Act.

C. Paradox of the Captive User

Our comparison of the platform type (Telehealth vs. Patient Portal) reveals a potentially dangerous market failure. Telehealth apps, which exist in a more competitive and open market place (apps like Teladoc, Doctors on Demand), show much lower friction in Availability (22%) compared to patient portals (37%). These results confirm the breakdown of the *Switching* mechanism proposed by Vaghefi and Tulu [3].

In a standard marketplace, users abandon unstable apps, forcing developers to fix bugs to survive. However, as discussed, users of patient portal apps are *captive audiences* tethered to their hospital's procurement choices. A user cannot switch hospitals or providers simply because they cannot access their portal. This lack of market pressure has allowed portal developers to neglect Availability without risking user retention, creating a *captive user paradox* where important apps for care continuity are the least available.

D. Privacy versus Availability

Our data highlights a critical misalignment between system design priorities and actual user needs. Users are overwhelmingly focused on Availability issues (mapped to Reliability in our framework) over privacy concerns. As seen in Fig. 2, our analysis reveals that users are 7.4x more likely to complain about technical failures than privacy risks. For the users, the inability to view a lab result is a more tangible threat than a theoretical data breach (Risks).

VI. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE RESEARCH

Although this study provides a large-scale analysis of mHealth perspectives on Availability, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, our data was collected from the Google Play Store, which allows us access to many patient portals and telehealth apps but excludes Apple's App Store apps. Therefore, our findings may not account for differences in app performance and user demographics, and may limit generalizability to other user populations.

As discussed, our dataset contains 67 different patient portal and telehealth apps, and although these apps represent a large user base, the results may not generalize to niche mHealth apps. In addition, while our dataset allows for more granular segmentation, our current study treats the mHealth ecosystem as a broader aggregate. In future studies, we will conduct a thorough analysis using advanced topic modeling techniques to further surface sub-themes under Availability. This would allow us to decompose generic crash reports into actionable categories to help us understand the exact nature of the technical issues.

Our usage of the class Availability relies on a supervised text classification model, and while our model demonstrates strong performance with high calibration and F-1 scores, future research would benefit from conducting qualitative user studies, such as interviews, questionnaires or surveys to capture the nuance and lived experience of the technical friction.

In addition, our dataset includes reviews from both smartphone and tablet users. While similar, their specific technical friction experienced on different devices was not part of our analysis. Future research should make the distinction between device type to determine if that disproportionately impacts the availability issues.

Finally, we also acknowledge the distinction between user expressed sentiment and actual behavioral outcomes. This discrepancy, referred to as *Attitude-Behavior Gap* [21] and further characterized in [20] as the *Privacy Paradox*, suggests that users often continue to use digital services despite expressing significant concerns, meaning expressed sentiment is not necessarily equal to actual usage. A similar paradox likely exists regarding Availability in the mHealth context. While our data quantifies the intensity of *expressed* availability friction (e.g., negative reviews), we lack the backend usage logs to measure *actual* attrition. Consequently, we cannot confirm whether these technical failures lead to the abandonment of the app or if users are forced to persist in using unstable systems due to the lack of alternative mechanisms for care.

VII. CONCLUSION

Our study makes three key contributions that have implications to the fields of Health Informatics, Human-Computer Interaction, and Human-Centered Cybersecurity.

- 1) We provide the first longitudinal analysis designed to test the technology maturity assumption, quantifying the regression of availability over a period of 14 years.
- 2) Based on our results, we do not find support for the "Stage Hypothesis" [1] in the mHealth context. While traditional IT systems evolve toward stability (*Maturity*), our findings show that a significant segment of the mHealth ecosystem (patient portal and telehealth apps) has regressed into instability (*Contagion*) since 2018.
- 3) We challenge the "Switching" mechanism proposed in user retention models [3]. Specifically, we found that "Captive users" of patient portals are likely unable to migrate away from unreliable infrastructure, creating a

unique security vulnerability where availability failures persist without correction.

As shown in our trend analysis, patient portal and telehealth apps, essential for the mHealth ecosystem, have not followed Nolan's linear path toward *Control*. Instead, we show that these apps experienced a post 2018 regression in which the apps effectively reverted to the Contagion phase. These results indicate that the rapid development of mHealth apps, along with the consistent addition of complex features, can destabilize technical availability.

The findings can also guide developers who create and maintain mHealth apps, especially those that process PHI. For instance, they should anticipate that Availability failures are likely to occur. Delayed responses to address such failures can lead to unintentional information blocking and result in a maximum penalty of \$ 1 million per violation [33]. Thus, mHealth app development should not only focus on Confidentiality and Integrity, but also on Availability given the potential financial loss due to Availability failures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Timoteo Kelly, gratefully acknowledges the support of the National Science Foundation and U.S. Office of Personnel Management CyberCorps Grant No. DGE-1946619. John Robert Bautista was supported by a start-up grant from the Sinclair School of Nursing, University of Missouri-Columbia.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. L. Nolan, "Managing the computer resource: A stage hypothesis," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 16, no. 7, pp. 399–405, 1973.
- [2] A. Kolukisa Tarhan, V. Garousi, O. Turetken, M. Soylemez, and S. Garossi, "Maturity assessment and maturity models in health care: A multivocal literature review," *Digital Health*, vol. 6, p. 2055207620914772, 2020.
- [3] I. Vaghefi and B. Tulu, "The continued use of mobile health apps: Insights from a longitudinal study," *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, vol. 7, no. 8, p. e12983, 2019.
- [4] C. Stephanidis *et al.*, "Seven HCI grand challenges," *Int. J. of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 35, no. 14, pp. 1229–1269, 2019.
- [5] F. D. Davis, "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 319–340, 1989.
- [6] D. H. McKnight, V. Choudhury, and C. Kacmar, "Developing and validating trust measures for e-commerce: An integrative typology," *Information Systems Research*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 334–359, 2002.
- [7] R. C. Mayer, J. H. Davis, and F. D. Schoorman, "An integrative model of organizational trust," *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 709–734, 1995.
- [8] R. A. Tamime, A. Farooq, J. Salminen, V. Marmion, and W. Hall, "Understanding privacy concerns in mobile health applications: A scenario-based online survey," in *Proc. IEEE TrustCom*, 2023, pp. 1757–1765.
- [9] *Security Standards for the Protection of Electronic Protected Health Information*, 45 C.F.R. § 164.306(a)(1), 2003.
- [10] J. Carvalho *et al.*, "Evaluating maturity models in healthcare information systems: A comprehensive review," *Healthcare*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2025.
- [11] 21st Century Cures Act, Public Law No. 114–255, §3022 (2016). Available: <https://www.congress.gov/bill/114th-congress/house-bill/34/text>
- [12] T. Kelly, A. Korkmaz, S. Mallet, C. Souders, S. Aliakbarpour, and P. Rao, "Longitudinal Datasets of Health App Reviews for Privacy and Trust Modeling," *Data in Brief*, art. no. 112740, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2026.112740>
- [13] T. Kelly, A. Korkmaz, S. Mallet, C. Souders, S. Aliakbarpour, and P. Rao, "HARPT: Health App Reviews for Privacy & Trust," *Harvard Dataverse*, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/U60F6F>
- [14] Dhagarra, D., Goswami, M., and Kumar, G. (2020). Impact of Trust and Privacy Concerns on Technology Acceptance in Healthcare: An Integrated Model. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 161, 120332.
- [15] Ruotsalainen, P., Blobel, B., and Pohjolainen, S. (2022). Privacy and Trust in eHealth: A Fuzzy Linguistic Solution for Calculating the Merit of Service. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 12(5), 657.
- [16] S. Spiekermann, "Perceived control: Scales for privacy in ubiquitous computing," *Digital Privacy*, 2007.
- [17] J. Zhang, J. Zhou, J. Hua, N. Niu, and C. Liu, "Mining user privacy concern topics from app reviews," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 222, p. 112355, 2025.
- [18] Joint Task Force, "Security and privacy controls for information systems and organizations," *National Institute of Standards and Technology*, NIST Special Publication 800-53 Rev. 5, 2020.
- [19] O. Haggag, J. Grundy, M. Abdelrazek, and S. Haggag, "A large scale analysis of mHealth app user reviews," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 7, p. 196, 2022.
- [20] S.Barth and M.D.T. de Jong, "The privacy paradox: Investigating discrepancies between expressed privacy concerns and actual behavior," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 1038–1058, 2017.
- [21] P. A. Norberg, D. R. Horne, and D. A. Horne, "The privacy paradox: Personal information disclosure intentions versus behaviors," *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 100–126, 2007.
- [22] Yang, Z., Dai, Z., Yang, Y., Carbonell, J., Salakhutdinov, R., and Le, Q. V. (2019). XLNet: Generalized Autoregressive Pretraining for Language Understanding. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 32.
- [23] Abdelhamid, M., Gaia, J., and Sanders, G. L. (2017). Putting the Focus Back on the Patient: How Privacy Concerns Affect Personal Health Information Sharing Intentions. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 19(9), e6877.
- [24] Esmaeilzadeh, P. (2020). The impacts of the privacy policy on individual trust in health information exchanges (HIEs). *Internet Research*, 30(3), 811–843.
- [25] Zhang, J., Zhou, J., Hua, J., Niu, N., and Liu, C. (2025). Mining user privacy concern topics from app reviews. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 222, 112355.
- [26] Cascini, F., Pantovic, A., Al-Ajlouni, Y. A., Puleo, V., Maio, L. D., and Ricciardi, W. Health data sharing attitudes towards primary and secondary use of data: a systematic review. *eClinicalMedicine*, 71, 102553, 2024.
- [27] N. K. Malhotra, S. S. Kim, and J. Agarwal, "Internet users' information privacy concerns (IUIPC): The construct, the scale, and a causal model," *Information Systems Research*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 336–355, 2004.
- [28] D. Gefen, E. Karahanna, and D. W. Straub, "Trust and TAM in online shopping: An integrated model," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 51–90, 2003.
- [29] S. Spiekermann, "Perceived control: Scales for privacy in ubiquitous computing," *Digital Privacy*, 2007.
- [30] T. Dinev and P. Hart, "An extended privacy calculus model for e-commerce transactions," *Information Systems Research*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 61–80, 2006.
- [31] J. Everson and D. Healy, "Information-blocking trends following regulatory action," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 665–674, 2025.
- [32] L. T. Hosmer, "Trust: The connecting link between organizational theory and philosophical ethics," *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 379–403, 1995.
- [33] Office of Inspector General, "Information Blocking," *U.S. Department of Health and Human Services*, Sep. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://oig.hhs.gov/reports/featured/information-blocking/>